

Language loss and translingual identities near the Navajo land

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As an instructor teaching a majority of Navajo students at a rural branch campus of a state research university near the Navajo reservation, I have observed that many of my Navajo students claim that they do not speak the Navajo language fluently. Data obtained through background forms and in-class writing exercises and observations suggested that a minority of the Navajo students claimed that they can hold a conversation or get by with another Navajo speaker in Navajo. Some of their parents never or hardly ever spoke the language to them, so they never learned the language. Some claimed that only their grandparents spoke the language to them. Due to moving to a different place, they lost their language proficiency because their parents never spoke the language to them. Some claimed that their grandparents passed away, so they lost their language proficiency. The majority of the Navajo students hope to learn or re-learn their language of heritage.

Keywords: Heritage Language; Language Loss; Language Shift; Navajo; Navajo Reservation; Translingual Identities

1. Introduction

As an instructor teaching a majority of Navajo students at a rural branch campus of a research university near the Navajo Reservation, I have observed that many of my Navajo students claimed that they do not speak the Navajo language fluently. In a questionnaire conducted in 1970 on over 3500 six-year-old Navajo children's knowledge of the Navajo language, the results concluded that only 6 % of the children were primary speakers of English with a little knowledge of Navajo and only 5% of them were monolingual speakers in English (Spolsky, 1975). Note that Spolsky's study took place more than 45 years ago. Obviously, the phenomenon today has shifted toward the opposite direction. A Navajo language instructor at a tribal college stated that 30 years ago almost 8 out of 10 students were fluent speakers of Navajo, but recently only 1 out of 10 is fluent speaker of the heritage language (Talahongva, 2018). House (2002) indicated that her students told her that many of the Navajo elders "do not want to talk to the youth" and "criticize and condemn their less than fluent performances in the Navajo language" (p. 54); perhaps the elders do not foresee the urgency of language loss.

Contrary to House's (2002) study, one of my students recently expressed that the elders often spoke about this young generation of Navajo not listening to them anymore because they do not want to speak Navajo. Another student stated that her grandmother blamed her mother during family gatherings for not teaching her how to speak Navajo. Another one of my students shared with the classmates the fact that the young Navajos who live on the reservation do not speak Navajo, even though their parents and guardians are fluent speakers of Navajo. This gave me flashbacks because my experience was similar to hers, as my parents never spoke their native language to me as I grew up. This and several years of experience teaching Navajo students made me contemplate this language shift phenomenon.

I acquired Min Nan—i.e., a Taiwanese dialect—from my grandmother who only spoke the language; however, my parents whose native language is also Min Nan only spoke Mandarin to me. My experience is similar to some of my students' personal experiences on this matter. They shared with me and the classmates that English is the primary language of instruction at school and basically once they step outside of their homes, they enter into a world of English where everyone speaks and learns English. As for me, Mandarin was the only language I was allowed to speak at school as a child. As a first grader, I remember that I would be punished for speaking a word of Min Nan in the classroom by a fine, a rule set up by my homeroom teacher. Even though many of my students claimed they were not fluent speakers of Navajo, I observed that during their oral presentations they often expressed that they hope to learn or re-learn their language of heritage. McNeil et al. (1999) emphasized that the Navajo college students hold a stronger ethnic identity than the students from other ethnic backgrounds (i.e., Asian American, Hispanic American, Caucasian, and mixed race).

In this paper, I explored my Navajo students' experiences of language loss and translingual identities through their perspectives in light of my own experiences based on the study in my English Composition and Introductory Linguistics classes.

2. Background

McCarty et al. (2006) indicated that the Navajo youth suffer from the "Long Walk Syndrome" (p. 671), which caused them to give up learning Navajo due to fear of punishment. By teaching the students for more than a decade, I observed that many of my students wrote about the Long Walk, an incident which took place in 1864 in which the Navajo people, including women and children, were forced by the American federal government to march from Fort Defiance, Arizona to Hwéeldi, Fort Sumner, New Mexico (Northern Arizona University, 2005). Tribal members were held for 4 years in Bosque Redondo.

They were eventually able to return home but with reduced land under “the Treaty of 1868 with the United States” (House, 2002, p. 4). Much evidence supported that the Navajo people viewed themselves as victims of the “American policies, practices, and values” (House, 2002, p. 40) due to this history.

Also, McCarty et al. (2006) emphasized that the Navajo youth have suffered from “self-hate” (p. 671) and were embarrassed to speak Navajo by claiming the “Navajo language is dumb” (p. 671). This negative sense of self not only affects heritage language maintenance but also the success of public school education on the reservation. The Native American’s “low self-esteem” and “lack of pride” in themselves (p. 162) are the primary reasons causing them to fail at school on the reservation (Little Soldier, 1989). Even their teachers held unconscious stereotypes against Native Americans or knew nothing about them due to American society’s having generally failed to recognize the contribution of Native Americans to the country (Little Soldier, 1989).

In Conn’s (2013) study on a reservation school, the high high-school dropout rates of Navajo youth are due to “shame and fear” (p. 9). The Navajo youth were ashamed of being Navajo, coming from the reservation, and their parents’ economic status, etc. (Conn, 2013, p. 9). The humiliation coming from the punishments for speaking the “barbarous” (p. 8) Native American languages also caused Native Americans to be ashamed of their native tongue and skin color and even instill a “distrust of education” (Ambler, 2000, p. 8). The history of boarding schools caused the Navajo to view English as superior and Navajo as inferior or even unnecessary, and caused them to view other Navajos who could speak proficient English as able to live modern, successful lives (Benally & Viri, 2005).

Some of my students claimed that once they entered elementary school, English became the primary language of daily use even though they once acquired Navajo from their grandparents. They claimed that all of their teachers and classmates spoke English. Peer pressure also took place in school. They mentioned being made fun of by their own peers for speaking Navajo at school. In McCarty et al.’s study (2006), some of the Navajo youth were judged for speaking the Navajo language by their peers as “uneducated” or the natives who never left the reservation (p. 670). Norton (2010) stated that language learners’ investments in the target language are associated with multiple factors which are not fixed or simplified and are constantly changing (p. 352).

I observed that more and more of my Navajo students claimed that they do not speak the language of heritage or are not fluent speakers because many of the Navajo youth were not spoken to in Navajo by their parents who spoke the language as stated by McCarty et al. (2006). My students have often mentioned the criticism they received from their family members and relatives once they

found out they were unable to understand conversation in Navajo during holiday or birthday get-togethers. They mentioned the odd looks, looks of disappointment, looks of shock, or judgements they received from the family members. They often expressed a sense of guilt they have experienced from within.

Due to this colonization—i.e., the history of Long Walk—Navajo people have internalized standards of what so-called good English should be and formed judgements of their own and other Navajo people's or students' Englishes (House, 2002). In McCarty et al.'s (2006) study, some of the Navajo youth had negative experiences being judged by people who spoke better English.

The influence of English on the Navajo language has been found in Webster's (2015) study, who wrote that Navajo English is common on the reservation. However, Webster (2015) conveyed that the Navajo had experienced "linguistic anxiety" (p. 55) for speaking a mixture of English and Navajo. The use of Navajo English can be criticized by both the Navajos and non-Navajos who might argue that standard English should be used instead (Webster, 2015).

One of my Navajo students wrote that his grandmother and parents decided that he would only learn English in order to succeed in American society. In Canagarajah's (2008) study of Sri Lankan Tamil families' language shift in migrated countries, the results suggested that due to the colonized history in Sri Lanka, the parents hold attitudes that English is superior to Tamil and they can obtain "benefits" (pp. 154-155) by learning English. Due to having been colonized by the UK in the past, they were treated as slaves. The parents forced the children to give up Tamil and learn English instead—because Tamil holds no economic benefits, but English can fulfill their children's "need and survival" (p. 165) in a migrated country where the primary language is English. As for the Navajo, the parents encourage the children to learn English because they hope that the children can fit into mainstream American society (Benally & Viri, 2005; McCarty et al., 2006).

The term, translingual, does not view each language as a separate entity, but views languages as overlapping entities (Jain, 2014). Any individual is not bound to this binary language ideology of native or non-native or monolingual or multilingual (Jain, 2014). This concept removes linguistic hierarchy, ownership of any language, and marginalization of any individual in any linguistic communities (Kim, 2021). The gap between these hierarchical constructs (e.g., native/non-native, etc.) is narrowed (Yazan & Rudolph, 2018), and translinguals' linguistic repertoires are legitimized (Kubota & Miller, 2017). Since many of the Navajo students have been taking Navajo language and culture classes offered at public school and college and some of them acquired Navajo from their grandparents, my Navajo students are not

constrained to this unequal language ideology as native or non-native speakers of Navajo. Many of them holding these translingual identities claimed they hope to learn or re-learn their heritage language.

3. Method

After consent forms were administered and collected, a background form collecting students' demographic information and personal experience on language was distributed at the beginning of the semester to two English Composition classes and one Introductory Linguistics class. An in-class writing exercise was then implemented to these two English Composition classes on a topic related to language learning experiences. General observation also took place during these three classes. Observation notes were taken. The majority of the students who participated are Navajo students due to the fact that the majority of the students enrolled in the college are also Navajo. To ensure validity, only the Navajo students were included.

I analyzed the forms, in-class writing exercises, and observation notes once they were completed. The data collection and analyses were conducted at the same time (cf. Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Coding and finding the themes were utilized during the analyzing process (cf. Bailey, 2007). I read the data several times, and during the process, I coded it and categorized the codes to form common themes.

4. Results

Based on the background forms, the results suggested that the majority of the participants are Navajo and a minority of Navajo students wrote that they can hold a conversation or function with another Navajo speaker in Navajo.

4.1. In-class writing results

The results from the in-class writing exercise are described here. One of the Navajo students stated that English is her first language. However, she tried to learn Navajo by speaking Navajo to her grandparents and parents whose first language is Navajo in hope to learn the language. However, when she tried to communicate with her parents in Navajo, they had trouble understanding her. She called her own Navajo "broken" because she had to switch back and forth from Navajo to English when speaking. As she is studying to become a nurse, she hopes to be capable of helping elders in her community and her future patients who only speak Navajo. She once was asked by a patient at hospital for help in Navajo; however, she could not help her even though she wanted to because she did not understand what the elder said in Navajo. She conveyed that learning Navajo is important to her as it connects to her heritage and culture. Furthermore, the Navajo language can help her communicate with her

future patients as becoming a nurse is her career goal and can allow her to integrate into her community from which she felt distanced.

Another student wrote that she never had anyone in her family who spoke to her in Navajo, but she picked up words in Navajo when she heard them as she got older. When she was a teenager, she did not understand why she had to learn the language and thought Navajo was “useless.” However, as she became an adult, she realized that not being able to speak the language makes her feel “useless” when she was not able to help an elder asking her for help and who only spoke the Navajo language. She also felt judged by her family and friends with “a look of disappointment and shock” when they found out she was unable to form sentences when speaking in Navajo. She then stated that to her speaking Navajo personally connects her to the Navajo people, and this makes her “feel proud.”

The other student revealed that she lost her ability to speak the Navajo language which she once was capable of because she was moved away from the reservation to a city in a different US state. Before moving, she learned Navajo as her native language from, “the best people,” her grandparents whose first language was Navajo. After moving, her mother made efforts to make sure she adapted to the new environment and wanted her to get rid of her accent from the reservation even though she claimed that the accent still sticks in her English until today. After several years, before her teens, she was moved back to the reservation, but she had lost her Navajo language. She could only speak “the basic words” that she learned as a little child from her grandparents but was unable to understand sentences or stories the people she loved spoke around her especially during family gatherings or holidays. She felt “guilty” for losing the language of heritage.

Another student wrote that English is the only language she acquired growing up and is her only family language. Her father who is a fluent speaker of Navajo would only speak Navajo to his side of the family. Her father only spoke certain words to her and her siblings in Navajo at home. She and her siblings memorized these Navajo words growing up. Now she uses them in her household even though English is her only language.

4.2. Class observation results

The results from the class observations are the following. During a group discussion in my Introductory Linguistics class, I heard one of my Navajo students say to another student that learning the English language is to be competitive in the national job market. He said learning the English language is to be “prosperous.” This group discussion took place right after we finished watching a video on code-mixing of two languages, Cantonese and English, in Hong Kong. The student revealed that his grandmother and parents decided

that he and the rest of the next generation will stop learning Navajo. They all will only speak English to survive within American society.

In another class discussion, one of my Navajo students shared with me and the classmates that those people who learned English in the video seemed so positive. He continued by saying, unlike here in America, the people here are more pessimistic, after we listened to the National Public Radio news story on a book comprised of a collection of essays written by learners from all over the world about how they learned English. The Navajo student then stated that Navajos had a history of boarding school, land removal, etc. The book editor and one of the contributors shared their experiences and understandings of how people from all over the world learned English. During the program, there was a call-in session where immigrants in the US shared their personal experiences learning English and what the difficulties learning English are for the people they knew whose first language is not English.

In English Composition class, during a group discussion on an article where the author who lost her language of heritage was eager to re-learn it, one student stated that she grew up living with her grandmother who only spoke Navajo. She then acquired Navajo from her grandmother, but she passed away a couple years later. When she was seven years old, she was fluent in Navajo. However, after her grandmother passed away, no one else in her family spoke the language to her. She then lost the language proficiency. Since then, English has become her primary language. When she hears someone speak Navajo, she feels that she has lost her identity because she is “full blood Native American” who doesn’t represent her “cultural language.” She then expressed her hope to make changes to re-connect to her culture of heritage.

The other student revealed that growing up she was always around the Navajo language and culture but was never able to pick it up. She can understand basic words in Navajo but is unable to pronounce words correctly and form sentences in speaking. She stated that as a Native American in the 21st century, she is aware of the fact that “I have helped my native people lose their tongue.” Not speaking fluent “*Diné Bizaad*” (Navajo language) is highly “frowned upon.” She stated that growing up she has been aware that the Navajo language is gradually “disappearing.”

Another student stated that when she was little, she used to live near her grandparents, so she acquired the Navajo language from them and could comprehend it very well but did not speak it fluently. Her parents were criticized for not speaking the Navajo language to her. When she was getting better at speaking the language, she was moved to Albuquerque. When she was moved back after several years, she had lost the language. She thought that as a “full blood” Navajo, she should have been fluent in her language of heritage. When family members and relatives visited, she would laugh at the jokes they

told her in Navajo pretending that she understood them; otherwise, her parents would get in trouble again. She herself would try to speak some Navajo words, but “nothing would come out. No matter how hard I try.” She expressed that she yearned to help the elderly but felt “guilty” that she would only comprehend a little bit in Navajo. She once tried to help an elder in the Navajo Nation Festival to unload her truck pretending that she understood what she was saying. The Navajo lady “got mad” at her and ended up having to communicate with her using hand gesture.

4.3. Overall results

Overall, some of the Navajo students believe that learning the Navajo language is unnecessary as all of their day-to-day lives involve only one language: English. Some of them shared that they were never spoken to in the language of heritage. Some acquired the Navajo language from their grandparents, but once they passed away, they lost proficiency in the language. Some of them were moved away from their grandparents who only spoke their language of heritage, so they lost the heritage language. Some of these students claimed that no one in the family was able to teach them their heritage language. Some of my Navajo students have expressed that they are aware that the majority of their generation do not speak Navajo fluently or even speak it at all. However, the majority of them hope to learn or re-learn their language of heritage to connect to the culture and help the elderly in their communities.

5. Discussion

One of my Navajo students in a group discussion in the Introductory Linguistics class brought up the boarding school experience that impacted the Navajo people’s attitudes and choices toward either their heritage language or the dominant language. House (2002) indicated that boarding schools in the early period indeed forbade Navajo students from speaking Navajo with humiliating punishments (p. 18); boarding schools, as such, are tantamount to what Foucault (1970, 1997) calls ‘panopticon’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021, 2023). Due to this history, some of the elders including grandparents view English as the advantageous language that can help the children get ahead and survive in American society. One of my students shared with me and the classmates that he attended a boarding school when he was young, but he was allowed to speak Navajo in the dormitory. Another student shared that she was sent to a boarding school far away from home. After she came home during the summer, she lost her Navajo language. As stated by House (2002), for the Navajo, the experiences of boarding school were not all negative.

The boarding school experience indeed made some of the Navajo grandparents and parents give up speaking the language of heritage to their next

generation—at least based on what a few of the Navajo students shared—in the hope that the young generation would be able to climb the social ladder and fit into American mainstream society. Another student pointed out the Navajo history of land removal associated with the history of Long Walk, caused generational trauma which caused the parents to stop speaking Navajo to their children and speak English instead. The Navajo parents who only speak English to the children hope that they will advance in American society since they are under the American federal government where English is the primary and dominant language. My Navajo students revealed that everything nowadays is in English, and everybody is learning English; moreover, a few of them revealed that they were stressed about learning English once enrolling in elementary school if they acquired Navajo as children.

Some of my Navajo students indicated that once they entered elementary school, English became the primary of language for school and everyday use; therefore, they lost the proficiency of Navajo language. The Navajo youth and teachers in McCarty et al.'s (2006) study mentioned that the assessment standards of the school system in the state also caused them to focus on learning English and “abandon heritage-language instruction” (p. 672). Some of my students also stated that English is the primary medium in almost everything they receive considering if the parents do not speak the Navajo language to them at home. Some of them acquired the Navajo language from grandparents, but once they passed away, the students mentioned that they lost the language proficiency since there was no one else speaking the language to them.

One of the Navajo students revealed that her mother moved her away from the reservation to a different US city and hoped that she could get rid of her accent from the reservation and acquire standard English. Due to the history of colonization and punishments for speaking the heritage language, the Navajo set up standards for what good English should be (House, 2002) and judge their own Navajo people who speak Navajo as uneducated and never having left the reservation (McCarty et al., 2006). Nonetheless, some of the Navajo students pointed out that they were criticized by family members and relatives for not being able to speak or comprehend the Navajo language and they felt “guilty” over it.

The Navajo have been suffering from poverty, high unemployment rates, and severe living conditions (e.g., no running water, no electricity, no broadband infrastructure, etc.) inhabiting their reservation. Based on the US Bureau of Labor Statistics (2022), the unemployment rates in December 2022 are high with 3.9% in New Mexico where the college is located and 4.0% in Arizona where the majority of the Navajo Nation is located. Many of the Navajo students who enrolled in the college inhabit the Navajo Reservation in Arizona which is

approximately 45 minutes away by vehicle to the college in New Mexico. According to the US Census Bureau, the annual income per capita from 2017-2021 is below \$24000 and the poverty rate is 28.2% where the college is located. In the Navajo Nation, the poverty rate is 38% which is twice or four times higher than the surrounding states in the US (Park, 2020). Moreover, one-third of the households on the Navajo Reservation live under harsh conditions without running water (e.g., no sink or toilet) or electricity (Cheetham, 2020) in their houses.

Additionally, the reservation lacks broadband infrastructure, and the internet if available is undependable (Park, 2020) and more expensive than other areas in the country (Park, 2020). Over half of the 109 Navajo communities do not have access to broadband internet. Furthermore, only 4 communities meet the speed standard for broadband set by the Federal Communications Commission (Park, 2020).

With the history of being dominated by the American government, the Navajo have been seeking ways to survive which includes encouraging their children to learn English in hope that they will be able to survive, fit in, and progress in mainstream American society (McCarty et al., 2006). Canagarajah (2008) emphasized that family cannot be completely held responsible for preserving the heritage language or language loss. Family is not a closed unit but receives outside influences. Family has to negotiate not only heritage language maintenance but also “social and economic pressures” (p. 171) in order to support the household. Family has been facing “material inequality and ideological dominance” (Canagarajah, 2008, p. 172). Due to the history and power of colonization¹ (Canagarajah, 2008), family has been prioritizing the advantage of English language over that of the heritage language which has economic advantages for their children to survive in the dominant society.

Even though there is a Navajo radio station, Navajo language and culture classes offered at all grade levels at school, the majority of my Navajo students claimed that they have been encountering difficulties learning the heritage language. They expressed the difficulties with pronunciation and of forming sentences in Navajo. Some of the Navajo students mentioned they decided to visit the grandparents to practice the heritage language. One of the Navajo students whose first language is English stated that even her parents forgot how to speak the Navajo language due to their everyday lives involving only English. Even though the Navajo language and culture class is offered at school, without parents’ and family members’ support and natural interaction in Navajo, the effect of the language learning could be limited.

The marginalization of the Navajo culture in the mainstream culture has negatively impacted the ways Navajos view their own heritage language and culture (Benally & Vin, 2005). Some of them do not see pride in themselves as

Native Americans or in their heritage language. The rare appearance of the Navajo culture in mass media causes Navajo children to be more interested in mainstream culture portrayed in English and to find Navajo language boring or “useless” as one of the Navajo students stated.

6. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, the majority of the Navajo students do not speak the Navajo language fluently. Language revitalization by promoting the Navajo language and its connection to the culture is urgent and necessary. In order to make heritage language revitalization successful, the efforts should focus on Native Americans’ “desired cultural practices and values” (p. 116)—e.g., recognition from the country, tribal or Native identities (Schwartz & Dobrin, 2016, p. 116). The Navajo also pay attention to their cultural heritage such as clans and traditional ceremonies where the Navajo language is spoken. Moreover, both family and community members are linguistic resources for the young. Parents, grandparents, and relatives who are able to speak Navajo no matter the level of proficiency, should speak to the children in Navajo since they were born. Teaching and speaking and learning the heritage language at home and in the communities can function as “a healing process” (Chew, 2015, p. 160) for the Navajo to counter the trauma from the history of the forced imprisonment, the Long Walk, and the punishment from speaking the heritage language, the boarding school.

Teachers and family and community members should emphasize to the younger generation the history of Navajo Code Talkers who helped the US military defeat the Japanese during World War II utilizing the Navajo language (Ambler, 2000; Gilbert, 2008). In this way, young Navajos can elevate their pride in being Native American and view the value of their heritage language.

The majority of the Navajo students claimed that they hope to learn and re-learn the Navajo language in order to connect to Navajo culture. They believe that their heritage language is the core to the culture. They hope to be able to communicate with the family members and the elders and connect to the communities by speaking the heritage language. The Navajo students hope that they will be able to help the elders who only speak the Navajo language by learning the language or re-obtaining the language proficiency. Contrarily, the heritage language also has its economic advantage as one of my Navajo students pointed out that she is studying to become a nurse and the Navajo language is useful to help her future patients who only speak the language.

Many of the Navajo students revealed that they took the Navajo language and culture class at public school, and they hope to learn their heritage language. A few of them mentioned that they learned how to speak some basic Navajo words by hearing them frequently. The majority of the Navajo students hold

translingual identities because they hope to learn or re-obtain the heritage language proficiency. They acquired the Navajo language as children from grandparents, picked up some Navajo basic words, or learned it at the Navajo language and culture class at school. However, most of the Navajo students claimed that they are not fluent speakers of Navajo. One of the students stated that she practiced speaking Navajo with her parents hoping to learn how to speak the language but ended up code-switching from Navajo to English.

All in all, the results show that some of the Navajo students' parents never or hardly ever spoke the heritage language to them, so they never learned the language. Some claimed that their grandparents only spoke the language to them; however, due to moving to a different place, they lost the language proficiency because their parents never spoke the language to them. Some claimed that their grandparents passed away, so they lost the language proficiency due to the fact that no one else in the family spoke the language to them. Because the Navajo students either acquired the heritage language at a very young age from grandparents, learned it at school by taking Navajo language and culture classes, or overheard the language spoken by parents or family members from time to time, they are translingual speakers/learners. In brief, the majority of the Navajo students hope to learn or re-learn the heritage language because the language connects them to the culture and represents who they are as the Navajo. The results of the study are, nevertheless, limited due to the nature of this qualitative study with a small number of subjects; this study took place at the college which is located at a border town, not on the reservation. Therefore, the results cannot fully reflect the Navajo's condition on the reservation.

Notes:

1. For more detailed discussion of language colonization and other related topics, see Balosa (2024), Chaka (2024), Kruger-Marais (2024), Mapuya (2024), Motaung (2024), Ndlangamandla (2024), Ndlangamandla et al. (2024), Nkhi and Shange (2024), Salmani Nodoushan (2024), and Xu and Fang (2024)—among others.

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References

- Ambler, M. (2000). Honoring native languages, defeating the shame. *Tribal College Journal*, 11(3), 8-9.
- Bailey, C. A. (2007). *A guide to qualitative field research* (2nd ed.). Pine Forge.
- Balosa, D. (2024). Existential sociolinguistics and existential justice: Addressing minority-language issues in multilingual societies. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2), 35-62.
- Benally, A., & Viri, D. (2005). Diné Bizaad [Navajo Language] at a crossroads: Extinction or renewal? *Bilingual Research Journal*, 29(1), 85-108.
- Canagarajah, A. S. (2008). Language shift and the family: Questions from the Sri Lankan Tamil diaspora. *Journal of Sociolinguistics*, 12(2), 143-176.
- Chaka, C. (2024). Multilingualism, translanguaging, diversity, equity, social justice, and activism: A tenuous nexus and misrepresentations? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 7-28.
- Cheetham, J. (2020, June 15). *Navajo Nation: The people battling America's worst coronavirus outbreak*. BBC News. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-us-canada-52941984>
- Chew, K. A. (2015). Family at the heart of Chickasaw language reclamation. *American Indian Quarterly*, 39(2), 154-179.
- Conn, D. R. (2013). When two worlds collide: Shared experiences of educating Navajos living off the reservation. *The Qualitative Report*, 18(25), 1-16.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage.
- Foucault, M. (1970). *The order of things: An archaeology of the human sciences*. Tavistock.
- Foucault, M. (1997). Space, knowledge and power, panopticon, of other spaces: Utopias and heterotopias. In N. Leach (Ed.), *Rethinking architecture: A reader in cultural theory* (pp. 350-356). Routledge.
- Gilbert, E. (2008). *Native American code talkers in World War II*. Osprey.

- House, D. (2002). *Language shift among the Navajos*. University of Arizona Press.
- Jain, R. (2014). Global Englishes, translinguistic identities, and translanguaging practices in a community college ESL classroom: A practitioner research reports. *TESOL Journal*, 5(3), 490-522.
- Kim, S. (2021). An autoethnography of trans-perspective development through translanguaging research and practice. In R. Jain, B. Yazan & S. Canagarajah (Eds.), *Transnational identities and practices in English language teaching: Critical inquiries from diverse practitioners* (pp. 127-144). Multilingual Matters.
- Kruger-Marais, E. (2024). Subtitling for language acquisition: Eye tracking as predictor of attention allocation in education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2), 129-150.
- Kubota, R., & Miller, E. R. (2017). Re-examining and re-envisioning criticality in language studies: Theories and praxis. *Critical Inquiry in Language Studies*, 14(2-3), 129-157.
- Little Soldier, L. (1989). Cooperative learning and the Native American student. *The Phi Delta Kappan*, 71(2), 161-163.
- Mapuya, M. (2024). Exploring the contribution of decolonisation epistemologies: Promoting social justice in accounting education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 131-155.
- McCarty, T. L., Romero-Little, M. E., & Zepeda, O. (2006). Native American youth discourses on language shift and retention: Ideological cross-currents and their implications for language planning. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 9(5), 659-677.
- McNeil, D., Kee, M., & Zvolensky, M. (1999). Culturally related anxiety and ethnic identity in Navajo college students. *Cultural Diversity & Ethnic Minority Psychology*, 5(1), 56-64.
- Motaung, L. B. (2024). Translanguaging pedagogical practice in a tutorial programme at a South African university. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 81-104.

- Ndlangamandla, S. C. (2024). The coloniality of English proficiency and EMI: Decolonization, language equity, and epistemic (in)justice. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 105-130.
- Ndlangamandla, S. C., Chaka C., Shange, T., & Shandu-Phetla, T. (2024). COVID-19 crosslinguistic and multimodal public health communication strategies: social justice or emergency political strategy? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2), 7-34.
- Nkhi, S. E., & Shange, T. (2024). The impact of pedagogical translanguaging in enhancing communicative competence of university students in Lesotho. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 29-52.
- Northern Arizona University. (2005). *The long walk: Indigenous voices of the Colorado Plateau*. https://library.nau.edu/speccoll/exhibits/indigenous_voices/navajo/longwalk.html
- Norton, B. (2010). Language and identity. In N. H. Hornberger & S. L. McKay (Eds.), *Sociolinguistics and language education* (pp. 349-369). Multilingual Matters.
- Park, C. (2020, October 12). *The cost of connectivity in the Navajo Nation*. New America. <https://www.newamerica.org/oti/reports/cost-connectivity-navajo-nation/>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021). Language and socialization? It is all about sociosemiotics. *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia del Linguaggio*, 15(2), 209-225. https://doi.org/10.4396/20212_07
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2023). EFL classroom, petri dish, panopticon, and free world: How do they merge through action research? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 17(1), 97-116. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7513356>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2024). Language colonization or lingua franca? Demystifying the status quo of Persian. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2), 63-90.
- Schwartz, S., & Dobrin, L. M. (2016). The cultures of Native North American language documentation and revitalization. *Reviews in Anthropology*, 45(2), 88-123.

- Spolsky, B. (1975). Linguistics in practice: The Navajo reading study. *Theory into Practice*, 14(5), 347-352.
- Talahongva, P. (2018). The knowledge holders: Imparting wisdom at tribal colleges and universities. *Tribal College Journal*, 29(4), 18-21.
- The US Bureau of Labor Statistics. (2022, December). *Local area unemployment statistics*. <https://www.bls.gov/lau/home.htm>
- United States Bureau. (n.d.). *Gallup city, New Mexico*. QuickFacts. <https://www.census.gov/quickfacts/gallupcitynewmexico>
- Webster, A. K. (2015). *Intimate grammars: An ethnography of Navajo poetry*. University of Arizona Press.
- Xu, Y., & Fang, F. (2024). Promoting educational equity: The implementation of translanguaging pedagogy in English language education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 53-80.
- Yazan, B., & Rudolph, N. (2018). Introduction: Apprehending, identity, experience, and (in)equality through and beyond binaries. In B. Yazan & N. Rudolph (Eds.), *Criticality, teacher identity, and (in)quality in English language teaching* (pp. 1-19). Springer.